

Resilience-Focused Monitoring Framework for Edge Systems

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Abstract—Developing applications on the edge is a difficult task, as issues arise when multiple nodes have to operate in unison. Common challenges comprise correctness, performance, and forensics analysis after a system crash. The challenges are aggravated when both edge and fog devices get in the picture, since the limited resources of some of them exacerbate any possible issue, and create the need for a robust mechanism to collect log data to make sense of the system’s behavior. The envisioned monitoring layer should collect log data regarding performance and errors, protect the data until they are delivered to an external data processing facility, and be easy to integrate into the deployed system. This paper proposes C-Mon, a resilience-focused monitoring framework for service-oriented applications that tests timing constraints against live log data. The monitoring framework is integrated with OpenAPI Generator, the mainstream ReST code generator we used to generate client and server interfaces and monitoring mechanisms. Log data are cached locally on the disk of the fog/edge devices and transferred to the monitoring server only when enough CPU cycles and network bandwidth are available, at the same time enabling forensics analysis.

Index Terms—Fog devices, caching, IoT, network monitoring, API generation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Monitoring of edge computing applications is becoming more critical as deployments become larger and more complex [1]. Monitoring can help reduce the system’s potential downtime by proactively keeping track of its states and enabling preventive actions before a critical error occurs. Performance monitoring can be used to activate elasticity capabilities when needed [2]. Finally, monitoring can help in troubleshooting after an error has occurred [3].

Representational State Transfer (ReST) [4] is an architectural style for handling communication between nodes. ReST is platform and language independent, and its most common implementation is built on top of the Hyper Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP). Nodes are either clients or servers; servers contain resources that represent services they provide, clients use HTTP methods to perform actions on the resource. Using ReST provides a convenient setup, as the paradigms at the basis of ReST are mainstream [4]. ReST reached a good degree of relevance for Edge applications and the Internet of Things (IoT) in general [5] [6], gaining acceptance on the whole spectrum ranging from hobbyist projects [7] to industrial applications [8].

When edge and fog devices are part of the picture, timing and safety properties are critically important since interactions with the physical world are inherently time-dependent. Current trends involve using techniques from the formal methods domain to verify edge applications timing properties before their deployment [9]. This involves preparing a realistic model of both the applications and the devices, which is however a complex error-prone task. Moreover, the timing characteristics of some operations such as wireless communication cannot be described with a hard constraint. Thus, it is necessary to monitor distributed systems built on top of edge devices to identify unexpected behavior and possibly cope with it.

This work proposes C-Mon, a constraint-based framework for edge devices interacting within a distributed system. This work improves on the state-of-the-art by:

- providing a platform that collects information from the edge device while it interacts with other devices;
- integrating the mainstream code generator OpenAPI Generator [10] into the development process to generate, based on an interface specification provided by the users, both the ReST endpoints for participating in the distributed system, and the code to gather data from the edge devices and send them to a monitoring server. This approach ease the learning curve for our approach;
- introducing in the picture a resilient-focused lazy queue, which allows to cache monitoring data locally on disk and send them to the monitor-server when enough CPU and bandwidth are available. This novelty allows to both limit the impact on the distributed application performance, and protect monitoring data against system failure for post-mortem forensics analysis.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: section II is devoted to background information about the systems used with C-Mon, as well as describes related works and compares them with C-Mon; section III describes the conceptual architecture of the C-Mon framework; section IV provides implementation details about C-Mon; section V presents a proof of concept used to perform experimental tests on C-Mon; section VI concludes the paper and suggests future work.

II. BACKGROUND

This section surveys necessary background knowledge and existing techniques, and it draws a comparison of related work to the proposed C-Mon framework.

A. Monitoring Techniques

Techniques for monitoring distributed systems can be compared along different aspects.

1) *Types of Monitoring*: In general terms, monitoring can be either **white-box** or **black-box**. [11] White-box monitoring implies that the monitored system exposes internal information (logs, state information, communication handlers, etc.). Black-box monitoring is based only on the information that is externally visible. Black-box monitoring is more readily available, whereas white-box monitoring can provide more information regarding what went wrong in particular.

2) *Monitoring Approaches*: Metrics of a monitored node can be gathered following four strategies: the agent-based, the agentless, the hybrid, and the data stream approach [12]. The **agent-based** approach uses agents, which are programs installed on the monitored node, with the role of gathering in-depth metrics. The **agentless** approach uses system built-in functionality and system protocols to gather monitoring data from a node. The **hybrid** approach combines the agent-based, used for more critical nodes, and agentless approaches in the same distributed system. The **data stream** approach is focused on scenarios where distributed systems are run on cloud environments. A data forwarder is installed on the nodes and transmits the monitored data to the monitor-server in real-time, and data can be used for example to raise alerts based on observed trends in the data.

3) *Data Collection Modes*: We consider three modes to transfer monitoring data to the monitor-server: pull, request and response, and push [12]. The monitoring data is prepared in advance on the monitored node for the **pull** mode, usually by an installed agent, cached locally, and the monitor-server has the responsibility to initiate the pull to get hold of the data. The **request and response** mode is typically used with the agentless approach. It is similar to the pull mode, but the data is not prepared in advance, and is related to current status only, thus limiting the access to historical information. For the **push mode**, gathered data are sent (or pushed) from the node to the monitor-server, either periodically, based on thresholds on the measured data themselves, or using more complex strategies.

B. Code Generation

Code generation is a general technique that concerns with many use cases, such as the creation of executable code or application models from the declarative description of what the application should do. [13]. Generally, there are four reasons to make use of code generation [14], which are Productivity, Simplicity, Portability, and Consistency.

We decided to employ code generation in our proposed approach. A few tools and techniques related to code generation are part of the picture, and they will be discussed in the rest of this subsection.

YAML [15] stands for “YAML Ain’t Markup Language”, and it is a language that can be used to store and exchange data between systems. C-Mon uses YAML to encode interface specifications, and as the source input for code generation.

An **OpenAPI Specification** [16] allows to describe a ReST interface either as a JSON documents or in the YAML language. An OpenAPI specification is composed by a number of object, the more important being the *paths* object, which lists the endpoints of the interface, the HTTP methods they support and the data formats consumed and produced by the endpoint.

Mustache [17] is a logic-less templating format, in the sense that it contains no looping or branching constructs, and instead, it operates solely using tags, which get expanded using values provided in a dictionary containing key-value pairs.

OpenAPI Generator [10] is a toolbox of generators used to generate client and server ReST APIs. OpenAPI Generator allows to specify the interface of APIs as OpenAPI specifications. OpenAPI Generator parses the specification into a dictionary and then feeds it to a language-specific generator, which is fundamentally a set of template files defined in the Mustache format. The output of the process is an implementation of the API written in the target language. To customize API generation, OpenAPI Generators allows to provide additional custom templates to be used during code generation, which in C-Mon’s case implement the monitoring functionalities.

C. Related Work

A few frameworks similar to C-Mon exist already, most relevant ones being “*Pivot tracing*” and “*RFDMon*”.

Pivot Tracing [18] allows users to define system properties to be analyzed at runtime. The Pivot Tracing framework appears to be a useful tool to expose programming errors, however, its queries work the current state only, and it is challenging to debug and replicate bugs using Pivot Tracing. On the contrary, our proposed C-Mon stores all data on the monitor-server, allowing to replicate bugs more easily.

RFDMon [19] was designed to monitor the system health of multiple nodes, for example, by collecting data on CPU, RAM, disk and network usage, temperature, fan speeds, and network availability of nodes. Our proposed C-Mon has the advantage of monitoring not only the local system state, but also other characteristics such as interaction timings.

Other monitoring systems, which do not comprise full monitoring frameworks, are “*Google Cloud*” and “*Graphite*”.

Google Cloud [20] is developed by Google Inc. and it can collect metrics and events from web-based services and display them on the Google Cloud website. However, it is not open-source and it does not allow customization and extension such as in the case of C-mon. Finally, **Graphite** [21] is a monitoring system that is built around a set of scalable real-time monitoring tools. The tools work by sending the monitored data to Graphite, which will store it in a specialized databases accessible via a built-in web interface. Graphite, like Google Cloud, can display the data, but it lacks C-Mon’s functionality to define constraints and check for violations thereof. Additionally, C-Mon provides a gentler learning curve because of its integration with a mainstream tool, OpenAPI Generator, while Graphite requires to master a set of complex and use case-specific tools.

Figure 1. Conceptual architecture of the C-Mon framework. The “system node” can denote both a server device and a client device

III. CONCEPTUAL ARCHITECTURE

The conceptual architecture for the C-Mon framework is presented in fig. 1. It consists of a system node, corresponding to either a server node or a client node and the monitor-server.

The **system node** consists of a *ReST API* which it uses to communicate with the monitor-server and other nodes. When two nodes interact, the *ReST API* block captures and abstracts away all business logic. Apart from that, this triggers the *Data Creator* which creates and enqueues the monitoring data into the *Queue*. The *Sender* dequeues the data and sends it to the monitor-server using the *ReST API*.

The **monitor-server** receives monitoring data from the nodes through its *ReST API*. The data are processed by the *Processor*, then handed over to the *Analyzer*, which informs the *Processor* of the result, and finally the *Processor* invokes the *Notifier*, if necessary.

A **lazy queue** (First In First Out discipline) was selected as a data structure, and in particular monitoring data are cached locally on disk until enough CPU and networking resources are available. The rationale behind this choice is that a) monitoring data are sent to the monitor-server in the order it was created, and the monitoring functions do not consume system resources when the node is under heavy workload.

In the current version of C-Mon, two monitoring properties are supported. Namely, the **timing property** monitors whether the time taken for communication between nodes is within the expected time, and if not, it causes the monitor-server to send a notification. The second property is current **network traffic** passing on the network interface of the IoT device, and it is simply logged on the monitor-server when received, to be available later when the distributed system is analyzed.

With regards to the taxonomies from section II-A, the C-Mon monitoring framework would be classified as a black-box monitoring system, since the information that is monitored can

be directly extrapolated from the data that are sent between nodes in the distributed system. Monitoring data are sent to the monitor-server using the push data collection mode, and the monitoring approach is agent-based.

When designing a system for **modifiability**, it is essential to identify the parts of the system that most likely will be modified and estimate the design cost to evolve the system, which however will reduce the cost of later modifications [22]. **Extensibility** permeates most of the design of C-Mon, as it is planned that C-Mon will be extended in the future. This allows users to enhance the framework as needed and eases the development of future versions. Extensibility has been achieved in the components of C-Mon by using a combination of polymorphism [23] from object-oriented programming languages and software design patterns [24].

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Mustache Implementation

The *ReST API* on the monitor-server and the monitor *ReST API* on the edge devices are created from the same API specification using OpenAPI Generator [10]. A client that is able to send monitoring data to the monitor-server was implemented by modifying the Mustache templates of OpenAPI Generator.

B. SQLite

When designing an edge application, it is important to plan for failure [25], for example since the chance of an edge or fog device failing increases as the number of nodes in the distributed system increases.

The lazy queue (see fig. 1) uses a SQLite database as a core component to ensure persistence of monitored data in case of system failure [26]. Whenever new monitoring data are created, they are immediately stored in a local SQLite database on non-volatile storage, meaning data will not be lost even if the process/system terminates abruptly. The data will remain in the SQLite database on the node until the monitor-server has correctly received them. Only after receiving an accepting HTTP response, is the data then deleted from the node’s local SQLite database.

The monitor-server persists all data received from nodes in its local SQLite database. After that, the monitor-server responds with an accepting HTTP code, allowing the node to purge the data from its own local SQLite database.

C. Scheduling

Scheduling in C-Mon is built on top of the “Quartz” job scheduling library [27], allowing the scheduling of tasks at specified intervals. Access to the scheduling functionality is also provided for the users of the C-Mon framework, allowing them to define their own tasks to schedule.

D. A more concrete view

The conceptual architecture (fig. 1) can be made more explicit by means of the UML Deployment diagram in fig. 2 and the UML Sequence chart in fig. 4, which refer to a use

Figure 2. UML Deployment Diagram

case of one client node, one server node, and the monitor-server.

Each node has a built-in *MonitorRestAPI client* that sends the monitoring data to the monitor-server via HTTP.

The monitor-server consists of a *MonitorRestAPI server* that receives the monitoring data from the nodes through HTTP requests. It then stores the data in a *PermanentDatabase*. These data are then retrieved by the *MonitorDataProcessor* and passed to the *ConstraintAnalyzer*, which checks the data against the defined constraints. These constraints are defined in a constraint specification provided to the monitor-server by a system administrator. If analysis of the data confirms a violated constraint, the *notifier* will inform the system administrator.

During deployment, a system administrator is intended to provide an API specification and a properties file to each edge device. The properties file allows to configure parts of the built-in functionalities such as, IP and port of the monitor-server, the age of monitoring data before it is cleaned,

location of the local message database, etc, as facilitated by the *ConfigurationManager*. Whenever the ReST API component sends or receives HTTP requests or responses, it prompts the *MonitorDataCreator* to create timing monitoring data, and then persist the data in a local database. The data are then later retrieved by the *MonitorDataSender*, which sends them to the monitor-server through the *MonitorRestAPI client*.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Use Case

Edge computing commonly used to handle distributed computing with high speed and scale in Banks and Finance. A net-banking system, represented in fig. 3, was developed to test C-Mon in a simulated but realistic scenario. The system consists of a single middleware node responsible for receiving and handling external requests while storing information in a single database node. The system functionalities exposed by the middleware are a) Create, delete, and retrieve users; b) Create, delete, and retrieve accounts for users, and c) Update and retrieve the balance of accounts. These functionalities are deemed to be adequately realistic without bringing unnecessary complexity.

In the use cases, time is critical, and delays in the request/response can have a considerable impact on the usability for the customers, leading to an investigation on the time cost of providing resilience to the monitoring data collection.

B. Overhead Test

We performed an overhead test to determine how much overhead is introduced by the C-Mon framework when used to monitor an edge application. The testing was done using the setup from fig. 3, where each node in the system and the monitor-server were run on different computers.

Figure 3. Use-case used for testing the C-Mon framework

Figure 4. Request Monitoring

A custom client was built to send a predefined series of requests to test the system. These requests were defined such that they called a mix of all the functionalities described in section V-A, to make the testing resemble a realistic scenario and not to skew the data towards a specific subset of operations.

A baseline was measured by running a series of tests without monitoring the systems. Later on, a series of tests were executed while monitoring the systems using C-Mon’s capabilities. To make the tests consistent, each series of requests was run on a fresh instance. Each test setup was repeated 20 times, with 500 requests sent for each test.

Initially, we compared the “Baseline” results with the “Monitoring”, which were obtained by running the C-Mon framework “as it is”.

Results of the tests are reported graphically in fig. 5, which depicts a Cumulative Distribution Function of each test; statistics on data are reported in table I. The calculated overhead in percentage for the “Monitoring” test compared to the “Baseline” amounts thus to 237.41%.

Given the high measured overhead, an investigation of the root-cause was executed. It was found that the bottleneck was the persistence of the monitoring data into the SQL database. The persistence of the monitoring data were made to run concurrently with the HTTP requests to remove this bottleneck, thus leading to the “Imprv.” (improved) monitoring tests, also reported in fig. 5 and in table I. The new test measured the overhead as 117 ms per request, which corresponds to 40% of the service time.

The test was thus able to estimate the cost of having data resistant against system failures. As predicted, there is a trade-off between performance and data resilience.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

C-Mon is a constraint-based monitoring framework for distributed systems. Its concept is to allow for monitoring edge devices that interact with each other and notify the user in case of a violation of a safety constraint. The applications run on the edge devices make use of a generated library for the interaction with an API, which also takes care of caching monitoring data locally and uploading the data to a monitoring server. The framework emphasizes robustness, ensuring data are retained in the event of process termination by persisting the data

Figure 5. Cumulative Distribution Function of the time needed to process a set of 500 request.

Test	# Request	AVG Time (ms)	AVG Time (ms/Request)
Baseline	10000	134639	270
Monitoring	10000	454949	911
Imprv. Monitoring	10000	188350	378
Imprv. Monitoring*	7000	192998	387

Table I

RESULTS OF OVERHEAD TESTING.

locally on the node. The C-Mon framework was showcased on a net-bank use-case, and it was possible to measure the delay caused by the robust monitoring capabilities of C-Mon, which allowed to estimate the trade-off between performance and data persistency.

Future work aims at monitoring additional properties of the nodes, comprising at least: system health properties such as CPU, disk and RAM usage; error properties such as generating errors from the 4xx and 5xx HTTP status codes. A mechanism to keep track of related events would enhance C-Mon's information by including a trace of all communications leading up to a violation. Two options to consider for the tracing depth are tracing on system node level - tracing the chain of nodes called - or on method level, tracing the internal stack of each node in the trace.

A user interface could significantly increase usability by giving near real-time access to aggregated data and gathering all the information in a central place in terms of interaction with the user. It could support the user while defining constraints and other configuration options, reducing the chance of user caused errors.

With regards to system performance, extending the concurrency of the components of C-Mon could significantly improve the performance of the framework. In this sense, we are planning to allow concurrent access to the data in the local caching database.

Finally, we plan to apply the C-Mon framework to a smart grid use case, since we see a good match between the C-Mon capabilities and the requirements of that use case.

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